

GENERATION OF MIL-HDBK-5 DESIGN ALLOWABLES FOR ARALL® LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

ARALL® Laminates* are a family of laminated hybrid composites structural sheet materials featuring high strength, low density, and high resistance to fatigue and fracture. They are composed of alternating bonded layers of high-strength aluminum sheet and unidirectional aramid fibers impregnated with epoxy adhesive resin. ARALL 3 Laminates, the ARALL type having the performance of improved toughness, corrosion, and formability, consist of multiple layers of anodizing 7475-T761 aluminum sheet, bonded by alternate layers of 3M AF-163-2U epoxy adhesive, impregnated with unidirectional aramid fibers.

In the development of design allowable properties for 2/1, 3/2, 4/3, and 5/4 ARALL lay-ups, a complex statistical experimental design consisting of three aluminum alloy production lots and five prepreg lots were included in the program. Two types of surface treatments for the aluminum alloy sheet, chromic acid, and phosphoric acid anodizing, were also investigated. All laminations were cured under four time/temperature autoclave cycles. The overall procedures for developing ARALL 3 Laminates static design allowables are presented. A modified MIL-HDBK-5E method was used in this study to statistically reduce test data for providing S-basis material properties for tension, compression, in-plane shear, and bearing. The failure modes of the specimens for each test

* ARALL® is a registered trademark for Alcoa.

were also examined and described.

KEYWORDS: ARALL® Laminates, Military Handbook, Design Allowable, Statistical Design, Failure Mode.

1. INTRODUCTION

ARALL Laminates are a new family of structural materials developed for fatigue critical applications requiring light-gage sheet [1-8]. These materials are bonded arrangements of thin aluminum alloy sheets and alternating plies of epoxy-adhesive impregnated with unidirectional aramid fibers (Figure 1). The principal benefit of the resulting hybrid composites is ability to impede and self-arrest crack growth attributed to the component of cyclic loading aligned with the fibers (generally also the direction of greatest tensile stress). Once a through-thickness fatigue crack develops in the aluminum layer, controlled delamination between the metal, epoxy, and fiber interfaces accommodates stress redistribution from the metal to unbroken fibers in the crack wake. The bridging provided by the strong aramid fibers constrains crack opening, thereby reducing the driving force for metal crack advance [1,2,9].

Figure 1. Alcoa ARALL® Laminates
Schematic of Standard 3/2 Layup

ARALL Laminates, pioneered at Delft University of Technology in the Netherlands in the early 1980s [1-6], are now commercially produced by Alcoa [7-8, 10-12]. Though originally developed for fatigue resistance, ARALL Laminates display a range of impressive, albeit directional, property improvements over those of monolithic high-strength aluminum, and they feature performance traits that compete with those of advanced composites [1-8]. These attractive characteristics include 15-20% lower density than aluminum; up to 60% higher strength than 7075 and 2024 aluminum at comparable stiffness; fabricability comparable to metal (e.g., it can be cut, sawed, drilled, joined, and inspected by conventional metal practices); ability of the outer metal layers to protect against fiber-resin system damage by moisture, thermal attacks, lightning strike, and impacts; and damping ability superior to monolithic aluminum. Envisioned aircraft usages include

tension-dominated fatigue and fracture critical structure (e.g., lower wing and fuselage skins), damping critical structure, lightning-strike areas, and structure requiring resistance to impacts, where attendant trade studies have identified potential for significant (15-40%) weight savings over current designs [3-6, 13-18]. Since October 1987, ARALL Laminates have been flying in the lower wing of a Fokker-50 prototype commercial transport aircraft [16], and Fokker and other airframers are evaluating the material for broader aircraft use. In addition, ARALL Laminates have been applied to the large cargo door of the C-17 military transport by Douglas Aircraft Company [19]. The orthogonal properties of ARALL Laminates made them ideally suited to handle the primarily circumferential stresses in the cargo door caused by cabin pressurization. Also, using ARALL Laminates has a 23% weight savings compared to aluminum in this application.

This paper describes the methodology and the results of the design allowables of ARALL 3 Laminates using a complex statistical experimental design. The design allowables presented here are useful for those aerospace designers.

2. STATISTICAL DESIGN

A complex statistical experimental design [20] listed in Table 1 was used in this study. Lay-ups of 2/1, 3/2, 4/3, and 5/4 of ARALL 3 Laminates were tested. Three production lots of aluminum alloy sheets and five aramid/epoxy prepreg lots were used. Two types of surface treatments for the aluminum alloy sheet, chromic acid and phosphoric acid anodizing, were also investigated. All laminations were cured under four time/temperature autoclave cycles. A total of 16 lots of various ARALL 3 Laminates as shown in Table 1 was fabricated for the development of design allowables. A series of static tests of MIL-HDBK-5E, tension, compression, in-plane shear, and bearing tests, were performed for developing the S-basis design allowables.

Table 1. Statistical Design Matrix for ARALL® Design Allowable Program

Panel No.	Configuration	Surface Treatment	Lamination Cycle	Aluminum Lot	Prepreg Lot
1	2/1	1	1	1	5
2	2/1	1	2	2	4
3	2/1	2	3	1	1
4	2/1	2	4	3	3
5	3/2	1	2	1	2
6	3/2	1	3	3	5
7	3/2	2	4	2	1
8	3/2	2	1	2	4
9	4/3	1	3	1	3
10	4/3	1	4	3	1
11	4/3	2	1	2	2
12	4/3	2	2	3	4
13	5/4	1	4	1	4
14	5/4	1	1	3	2
15	5/4	2	2	2	3
16	5/4	2	3	2	5

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

3.1 Materials ARALL 3 Laminates are 7475-T761-based, has nominal 0.4% postcure stretch, and is intended for high fatigue loaded structures together with high compressive loadings. The laminates use a 250°F (121°C) cure resin prepreg with a recommended service temperature of 200°F (93°C). Nominal thickness of the individual aluminum sheet layers is 0.012-in. (0.3-mm), and the prepreg nominal thickness is 0.0085-in. (0.22-mm). Standard laminate configurations vary from a 2/1 (two layers of aluminum surrounding one layer of prepreg), which is 0.032-in. (0.81-mm) thick, to a 5/4 (five layers of aluminum with four prepreg layers interspaced), which is 0.094-in. (2.39-mm) thick.

3.2 Primary Static Tests In this program, the tension, compression, in-plane Iosipescu shear, and pin-type bearing tests were performed. Ultimate strength, yield strength, modulus, Poisson's ratio, and density were measured per each configuration and per each test direction. All the test procedures were based on Alcoa ARALL testing procedures as described in Reference 21. A minimum of sextuplet test specimens is needed for each property determination for each lot.

3.3 Fractography Study The failure modes of the specimens from each type of test were examined under a scanning electron microscope. The predominant failure modes were identified for each type of test.

4. METHODOLOGY OF DESIGN ALLOWABLES

4.1 Definitions of Design Allowables MIL-HDBK-5E has defined the room-temperature design allowables into the following categories:

- A-Basis: At least 99 percent of the population of values is expected to equal or exceed the A-basis mechanical property allowable, with a confidence of 95 percent.
- B-Basis: At least 90 percent of the population of values is expected to equal or exceed the B-basis mechanical property allowable, with a confidence of 95 percent.
- S-Basis: The S value is the minimum value specified by the governing federal, military, or industry specification for the material. Statistical assurance associated with this value is not known.
- Typical Basis: The typical property value is an average value and has no statistical assurance associated with it.

4.2 Direct Computational Procedure Direct computation of A and B allowables requires adequate data to determine (1) form of distribution; and (2) reliable estimates of population mean and standard deviation for the normal distribution or reliable estimates of population threshold, shape, and scale parameters for the Weibull distribution. Determination of an A value requires at least 300 individual observations and determination of a B value requires at least 100 individual observations. To compute an A value for TUS(F_{tu}) at $x = x_0$, Equation (1) is used,

$$A = a + bx_0 - K'_A s_y \quad (1)$$

where a, b, and s_y are computed in the regression of TUS data, K'_A is $\sqrt{(1+\Delta)/n}$ times the 0.95th quantile of noncentral t distribution with noncentrality parameter $2.326/\sqrt{(1+\Delta)/n}$ and $n-2$ degrees of freedom, and

$$\Delta = \frac{(x_0 - \sum x/n)^2}{\sum(x - \sum x/n)^2/n} \quad (2)$$

The equation for computing a B value is similar with K'_B being used in place of K'_A . K'_B is $\sqrt{(1+\Delta)/n}$ times the 0.95th percentile of noncentral t distribution with noncentrality parameter $1.282 \sqrt{(1+\Delta)/n}$ and $n-2$ degrees of freedom, where Δ is defined above.

4.3 Reduced Ratio Computational Procedure A modified reduced ratio computational procedure of MIL-HDBK-5E based on the metal volume fraction approach was used for the determination of design allowables. Each of derived property was determined by its relationship to an established tensile property. This conservative pre-determined tensile properties were first approved by the Aerospace Material Specification of SAE.

This procedure involves pairing of individual TUS, SUS, or BUS measurements with TUS measurements for which F_{tu} has been established. This indirect method of computation is applicable to F_{tu} and F_{ty} in L and LT test directions other than the specified testing direction. It also involves pairing of individual TYS, CYS, SYS, and BYS measurements with TYS measurements for which F_{ty} has been established. This technique is based on the premise that the mean ratio of paired observations representing related properties provided an estimate of the ratio of corresponding population means. The ratio consists of individual measurements of property to be derived as the numerator and measurement of the established tensile property as the denominator. Thus, TUS or TYS in the specified testing direction always appears in the denominator of the ratio of observed values.

Three assumptions are required for the reduced ratio procedure:

- 1) Two properties must be distributed according to a bivariate normal distribution.
- 2) Coefficient of variation must be the same for the two properties.

- 3) Average of the ratio of two properties must be well described by a linear function of the independent variable.

Regression analysis is also used to determine reduced ratios when an allowable for a property, such as SUS, is computed indirectly from an already established allowable for TUS. The confidence level associated with allowables computed using the reduced ratio technique may be somewhat below 95%. To compute the reduced ratio at $x = x_0$, Equation (3) is used.

$$\text{Reduced Ratio} = a + bx_0 - t_{0.95} s_y \sqrt{(1 + \Delta) / n} \quad (3)$$

where Δ is defined in Equation (2), a , b , and s_y are computed in regression of SUS/TUS data, and $t_{0.95}$ is selected from the statistical table of t-distribution corresponding to $n-2$ degrees of freedom. The allowable for SUS (F_{SU}) at x_0 is then computed as

$$F_{SU} = (\text{Reduced Ratio}) \times F_{TU} \quad (4)$$

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Density Due to the low density of the aramid prepreg layers, the net density of ARALL Laminates is lower than that of monolithic aluminum. The plot of Figure 2 shows that increasing laminate thickness (or decreasing aluminum volume fraction) by increasing the number of plies reduced density to an asymptotic limit of about 80% that of solid aluminum.

Figure 2. ARALL®3 Laminates Density versus Aluminum Volume Fraction

5.2 Tension The tensile ultimate strength in the longitudinal direction is significantly better than those of the respective aluminum counterparts. However, the fibers contribute little to the transverse properties. The isotropic aluminum is advantageous when loading is multidirectional. The tensile yield properties are linked to plastic strength of the metal layers. The higher longitudinal tensile yield strengths over monolithic material are, in part, attributed to aluminum hardening during stretching and, in part, due to the post-stretch residual compression in the metal layers. Typical tensile stress-strain behaviors of 3/2

configuration are plotted in Figure 3. Figure 4 shows the relation between tensile strengths and metal volume fraction. It is clear that the tensile strengths increase as the metal volume fraction decreases in the longitudinal direction. This is because that the unidirectional fiber dominates the tensile behavior. However, the tensile strengths increase as the metal volume fraction increases in the transverse direction. This is because that the transverse property is mainly dominated by metal.

Figure 3. Typical Tensile Stress-Strain Curves for 3/2 ARALL®3 Laminates at Room Temperature

Figure 4. ARALL®3 Laminates Tensile Strength versus Aluminum Volume Fraction

5.3 Compression The longitudinal and transverse compressive yield strengths are comparable since the fibers contribute little in compression. Typical compressive stress-strain curves of 3/2 configuration are given in Figure 5. The compressive yield strength in both longitudinal and transverse directions increase as the metal volume fraction increases as shown in Figure 6. This indicates that the compressive properties are predominant by metal.

Figure 5. Typical Compressive Stress-Strain Curves for 3/2 ARALL®3 Laminates at Room Temperature

Figure 6. ARALL®3 Laminates Compressive Strength versus Aluminum Volume Fraction

5.4 **Shear** Historically, much of the thin-aluminum-sheet data appearing in MIL-HDBK-5 was developed by the blanking (punch) shear test method. However, the in-plane Iosipescu shear test has been used for the determination of the shear mechanical properties for ARALL Laminates. Typical in-plane shear stress-strain behaviors of 3/2 configuration are plotted in Figure 7. The shear yield strength in both longitudinal and transverse directions increases as the metal volume fraction increases shown in Figure 8. The shear ultimate strength in the transverse direction has the same trend also plotted in Figure 8. The shear ultimate strength in the longitudinal direction is not reported since plastic buckling often precedes failure in shear or the test ran out of travel of test fixture.

Figure 7. Typical In-Plane Iosipescu Shear Stress-Strain Curves for 3/2 ARALL®3 Laminates

Figure 8. ARALL®3 Laminates In-Plane Shear Strength versus Aluminum Volume Fraction

5.5 **Bearing** In the pin-loaded bearing test, e/D (ratio of edge distance to hole diameter) equals to 1.5 and 2.0 were performed. The bearing strengths in the transverse direction increase as the metal volume fraction increases. However, the bearing strengths in the longitudinal direction decrease significantly from $V_f = 73.8\%$ to $V_f = 67.9\%$. The bearing strength seems to keep constant as from $V_f = 67.9\%$ to $V_f = 63.8\%$. These plots are shown in Figures 9 and 10.

Figure 9. ARALL®3 Laminates Pin-Load Bearing Strength versus Aluminum Volume Fraction ($e/D = 1.5$)

Figure 10. ARALL®3 Laminates Pin-Load Bearing Strength versus Aluminum Volume Fraction ($e/D = 2.0$)

5.6 **Design Allowable** A modified reduced ratio computational procedure was employed in the regression analysis. Historically, the design allowable for all the aluminum alloys was developed using the thickness approach. In the present work, the metal volume fraction approach was used in the analysis. Based on the methodology previously

described in Section 4, the MIL-HDBK-5 design allowables for ARALL 3 Laminates were established. These allowables are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. MIL-HDBK-5 Design Allowables for ARALL® 3 Laminates

Specification	AMS 4302 (AMS 4302A Proposed)			
	Sheet Laminate			
	2/1	3/2	4/3	5/4
Form				
Laminate Lay-up	2/1	3/2	4/3	5/4
Aluminum volume fraction, %	73.8	67.9	65.3	63.8
Basis	S	S	S	S
Mechanical Properties:				
F _{tu} , ksi:	103*	111*	114*	116*
L	56*	51*	50*	48*
LT				
F _{ty} , ksi:				
L	76*	82*	82*	84*
LT	48*	43*	42*	40*
F _{cy} , ksi:				
L	46	46	44	44
LT	52	48	47	45
F _{su} , ksi:				
L†	--	--	--	--
LT	35	33	33	32
F _{sy} , ksi	25	23	22	21
L	25	24	22	22
LT	24	23	22	21
F _{bru} , ksi:				
L(e/D = 1.5)	90	86	83	82
LT(e/D = 1.5)	100	90	87	83
L(e/D = 2.0)	106	95	89	85
LT(e/D = 2.0)	111	93	87	81
F _{bry} , ksi:				
L(e/D = 1.5)	71	70	67	67
LT(e/D = 1.5)	76	71	71	68
L(e/D = 2.0)	82	81	78	77
LT(e/D = 2.0)	84	78	77	73
ε _f , Percent:				
L	1.5	1.8	1.7	1.8
LT	6.1	6.4	6.3	6.6
E, 10 ³ ksi:				
L	9.8	9.9	10.0	9.8
LT	7.7	7.1	6.7	6.7
Ec, 10 ³ ksi:				
L	9.6	9.6	9.6	9.7
LT	7.8	7.3	7.0	6.9
G, 10 ³ ksi:				
L	2.8	2.6	2.3	2.3
LT	2.6	2.4	2.3	2.3
μ:				
L			0.35	
LT			0.25	
Physical Properties:				
ρ, lb/in. ³	0.085	0.083	0.082	0.081
C, K, and α	NA	NA	NA	NA

* Specified

† F_{su} not obtained on longitudinal direction specimens due to insufficient travel of test fixture.

The data contained in this table represent an average of six specimens tested for each mechanical property.

5.7 Fractography Study The failure modes of above tests have been examined. The longitudinal tension specimen showed a local brittle failure rather than a global longitudinal splitting like common fibrous composites. The transverse tension specimen showed epoxy tensile failure and fiber-matrix debonding/splitting. Very little kink band deformation was

observed from the compression test. This is because the test only loaded to the 0.2% offset yield. The test did not reach the ultimate failure because the specimen always preceded plastic buckling. In the in-plane Iosipescu shear test, a fiber/matrix shear failure was predominant in the transverse specimen. However, a significant amount of deformation was found in the longitudinal specimen which did not fail during the test. The crushing failure mode is the common failure mode in the bearing test. Furthermore, the shear failure and shear-tension failure are also possible exhibited in the longitudinal specimens. The photographs of failure modes for these aforementioned test specimens are shown in Figure 11.

Tension:

Shear:

Compression:

Bearing:

Figure 11. Failure Modes of MIL-HDBK-5 Static Strength Test Specimens

6. CONCLUSIONS

A complete MIL-HDBK-5 design allowable table for ARALL 3 Laminates has been established using the metal volume fraction approach. Most of the mechanical properties of ARALL Laminates are metal-dominated except the tensile ultimate strength dominated by the fibers. Failure modes corresponding to each type of mechanical tests in the MIL-HDBK-5 program are also reported.

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